

FAIRagro International Collaborations and Partnerships (2025)

Introduction

FAIRagro is embedded in a broad landscape of international initiatives, scientific networks, and research infrastructures in which consortium partners already take leading roles or are actively engaged. The consortium benefits from these connections by aligning with accepted standards, sustainable service operation and contributing to the implementation of international directives. Strengthening these links is essential for ensuring the broad acceptance of services, outreach and international visibility of FAIRagro, advancing data-driven innovations, and positioning the agrosystem research community within the global Open Science ecosystem.

Rationale for a coordinated International Strategy

Many FAIRagro partners maintain extensive international contacts relevant to the consortium's mission. These activities have so far been largely bottom-up; the strategy presented here seeks to better coordinate and amplify them to build purposeful and sustainable international collaborations. FAIRagro strives to learn from the existing well-established international initiatives to strengthen scientific exchange, enhancing global interoperability, and reinforcing FAIRagro's role as a key contributor to agrosystem research data infrastructures. Knowledge exchange will be facilitated through workshops, participation in international networks, and by welcoming international colleagues into FAIRagro's discussions, working groups, and events.

Partnerships identified by the Steering Committee

At the FAIRagro Steering Committee Retreat on 15 November 2023, three partners were identified as initial strategic priorities: **AgMIP**, **CGIAR**, and the **Wageningen Data Competence Center (WDCC)**. In addition, FAIRagro maintains closely aligned collaborations with key European institutions, particularly **INRAE** and the **Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU)**, which play essential roles in areas such as semantics, interoperability, crop modelling, and professionalised data stewardship. Together with other organizations, these institutions form the core of FAIRagro's emerging European network for RDM in agricultural sciences.

Broader International Network and Global Initiatives

Beyond these primary partners, FAIRagro engage in numerous international activities communities and infrastructures (e.g., RDA, EOSC, GAIA-X, MACSUR, GLTEN, ELIXIR, GBIF, MIAPPE, AGROVOC) to support the development, harmonisation, and reuse of data, tools, and standards. These links ensure that FAIRagro remains interoperable with European and global infrastructures and that its services evolve in line with international best practices and user needs.

Strategic measures to integrate FAIRagro into the international agricultural RDM

Community Advisory Board (CAB) and Associated Partners (AP)

FAIRagro extended its international engagement and visibility through “Associated Partnerships” (AP) and strategic involvement of renowned scientists within a “Community Advisory Board” (CAB). It increasingly orchestrates the partners contributions to global research communities, and creates spaces for exchange by organising workshops, presenting results in international fora, and inviting international colleagues to participate in FAIRagro discussions, working groups, and activities and vice versa. A LoS is not obligatory but can describe how mutual support will be structured. APs and CAB members have no legal status but will be integrated into decisions about major strategic directions of FAIRagro in an advisory capacity for mutual benefit.

FAIRagro’s strategic partnerships

Collaboration with AgMIP

The Agricultural Model Intercomparison and Improvement Project (AgMIP, <https://agmip.org/>) is an international partnership that advances agricultural models and scientific and technological capabilities for assessing the sustainability of agricultural systems. AgMIP conducts coordinated multi-model assessments to analyse how climate impacts, climate variability and change, as well as other driving forces affect agriculture, food security, and poverty at local to global scales. AgMIP incorporates state-of-the-art climate, crop, and agricultural economic model improvements into coordinated regional and global assessments of current and future climate impacts and performs multi-model integrated regional and global assessments of technology and policy options for increasing food security and adapting to current and future climate risks by utilizing multiple models, scenarios, locations, crops and participants to explore uncertainty in climate and agricultural productivity and the effects of data and methodological choices.

FAIRagro objectives from this collaboration:

1. Understand international modelling activities and trends to explore synergies with FAIRagro’s data-focused work
2. Increase the visibility of FAIRagro within the international climate change impact modelling community
3. Exchange knowledge on data tools, workflows and development approaches
4. Collaborate on shared data challenges and joint tool development

Collaboration with CGIAR

The Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR) is a strategic global partnership of some 60 members and aimed to ensure sustainable food security and to reduce poverty and hunger in developing countries through research. CGIAR has different research centers (e.g. CIMMYT) and provides the (meta) data publisher [GARDIAN](#) (Global Agricultural Research Data Innovation Acceleration Network). GARDIAN is a metadata harvester, providing publications and data with enriched metadata and links across them where possible.

FAIRagro objectives from this collaboration:

1. Leverage synergies between FAIRagro and CGIAR
2. Benefit from CGIAR's wealth of experience in an international context
3. Improvement and integration of the FAIR Assessment Tool
4. Exchange and integration of Middleware between CGIAR and FAIRagro

Collaboration with INRAE

The Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement (INRAE) is one of the world's leading institutions in agricultural and environmental research. It is engaged in international data and research infrastructure initiatives such as AgMIP and the European Partnership "Agriculture of Data" (AgData) and it is one of the partners operating the AgroPortal ontology registry. FAIRagro and INRAE share strategic interfaces in the areas of semantics, interoperability, and data-driven agrifood systems. Since 2024, the collaboration is anchored in the FAIRagro CAB with two INRAE representatives (Clement Jonquet and Pierre Martre).

FAIRagro objectives from this collaboration:

1. Contribute expertise on semantics, ontologies, and crop modelling
2. Provide crop-model relevant data for Use Case 6 and support the development of interoperable, FAIR data flows for model integration
3. Provide the URGI unit to jointly implement services and data flows for FAIR Digital Objects in agronomy. Focus' are the application of standards (RO-CRATE, MIAPPE), to expose AI ready data sets
4. Reuse, sharing and integration of semantic resources through AgroPortal.

Collaboration with the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU):

Representatives from SLU's Data Management Support, together with WDCC representatives form the backbone and starting point of FAIRagro's European network activities with European partners on RDM in the agricultural sciences.

FAIRagro objectives from this collaboration:

1. Exchange and jointly discuss RDM workflows, helpdesk-practices, repository approaches, long-term experiment data management, and legal aspects
2. Establish embedded or associated Data Steward roles as a means to broaden domain-specific expertise across institutions

Collaboration with Wageningen Data Competence Center (WDCC)

The WDCC is part of the Wageningen University and Research (WUR) and supports research data management, data science, and artificial intelligence across the institution. It coordinates a network of more than 150 embedded data stewards and continuously develops innovative methods to improve data management and reuse.

FAIRagro objectives from this collaboration:

1. Strengthen data quality and institutional data-sharing practices
2. Exchange best practices on data stewardship, including the role, focus, and embedding of data stewards, as well as sustainable funding models
3. Explore approaches for data reuse and data science, including model and software publication workflows, mutual data harvesting, and methods to close the loop between data creation and data reuse

Important international collaboration partners and networks

Beside the strategic partnerships, FAIRagro's (co-)applicants are connected and/or actively involved with/in several international organizations, networks, institutions and associations:

- **Agroscope:** Agroscope belongs to the Swiss Confederation and is a major and well-known European player in agricultural research. Together with WDCC and SLU, Agroscope is part of our European Associated Data Steward Network and will include the Swiss perspective, especially concerning their food-environment interactions.
- **AGROVOC Multilingual Thesaurus (FAO):** KTBL and ZALF belong to the editorial board of the internationally accepted standard, maintain the German language translations and can introduce new concepts into this semantic resource based on demand and consensus with the editorial community.
- **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC):** Members of FAIRagro are already stakeholders of the EOSC, with the most prominent activity being the building of an RDI and an umbrella for the activities in the different research communities and EU member states. FAIRagro members participate in EOSC workgroups e.g. to ensure FAIRagro service interoperability with EOSC functionalities. With our activities, FAIRagro will ensure the information flow and coordination of activities between the agrosystem domain in Germany and Europe.
- **GAIA-X and European Data Spaces:** ZALF and Thünen Institute, assumed the leadership of the working group Science/Economy - Data Exchange for Research Purposes of the GAIA-X domain Agriculture, ensuring close cooperation with GAIA-X on the European level and identifying possible ways to align FAIRagro and GAIA-X services. KTBL was in the advisory board of the European Agricultural Data Space Coordinating and Support Action.
- **International Soil Modelling Consortium (ISMC):** Engagements from FAIRagro partners to ISMC networks and communities from data users help FAIRagro to develop services along demands of the international modelling community, as well as general research interests. The Thünen Institute leads the AGMEMOD consortium, in which one of the key activities is the collection, harmonization, compilation and distribution of the AGMEMOD datasets across different EU modelling teams.

- **LTE data networks:** FAIRagro partners cooperate closely with BonaRes, GLTEN (GLTEN, 2021), EJP Soil, and IOSDV. These networks will support our ambitions of harmonizing the publication of long-term experiments and will be used to implement our guidelines and recommendations on an international level.
- **MACSUR:** Researchers from the FAIRagro consortium have been leading partners in the European MACSUR Knowledge Hub. FAIRagro strives to build on this network and connect the data provision and preparation with the user-side demands from the modelling community. With MACSUR SciPol (coordinated by ZALF), FAIRagro will have the opportunity to directly implement and validate a workflow on direct access data and automatic processing of data to be directly used in simulation models.
- **Networks in plant sciences:** Partners of FAIRagro play an active role in steering committees for data standardization and exchange initiatives, e.g., Breeding API (BrAPI), the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and MIAPPE, and will consequently foster the integration of international standards into FAIRagro's RDM and policies. ELIXIR is the panEuropean infrastructure for biological information supporting research in life science and its transfer to the environment, bioindustries and society. FAIRagro partners BLU, IPK, and FZJ are members of ELIXIR-DE. We will coordinate existing infrastructure efforts within the ELIXIR Plant Community, Data Platform and several Commissioned Services to align with our services with international developments.
- **Networks in soil sciences:** Partners of FAIRagro are members of the EJP Soil Programme that have positions and hold positions on the Ethics Board and are National Communication Representative and Programme Manager, IUSS and EGU Division Soil Science Systems (SSS). Thünen advises the BMEL on the establishment of a soil database and on the FAO Global/European Soil Partnership, within which it is involved in various working groups. This arrangement ensures close connections among soil research projects on an international level and the promotion of the development of FAIRagro in these communities.
- **Research Data Alliance (RDA):** FAIRagro partners are active in various RDA working and interest groups, e.g., Data Citation WG, Biodiversity Data Integration IG and Interest Group Agricultural Data (IGAD). Some key results of RDA groups will be considered and could be implemented in consortia with a very strong mutual interest in the respective developments.

Furthermore, FAIRagro co-applicants are active members within international initiatives and efforts, e.g., Bioschemas, CODATA, OGC, DataCite, IPPN, EMPHASIS-PREP, ENVRI-FAIR, TDWG, OBO, eLTER, DiSSCo or IPBES.